

Project no.:
763959

Project acronym:
MegaRoller

Project full title:
**Developing the PTO of the first MW-level
Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage

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Table of Contents

	Page
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC	9
2 MEGAROLLER WEBSITE	10
3 BLOGS	12
4 PRESS & MEDIA	13
5 NEWSLETTERS	15
6 SOCIAL MEDIA AND VIDEO	16
7 COMMUNICATION KPI'S AND FINAL NUMBERS	20

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a project with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 763959. The project developed and demonstrated a Power Take-Off unit for wave energy converters.

The communication report applies to external communication and public outreach of results in the project.

The report gives the final status of the external communication activities that took place in the consortium since project start and how this relates the activities set out in the original communication plan (D6.1) and revised communication plan included as part of the first communications report (D6.7). This report refers to activities done throughout the entire project, including activities already covered in the first communications report.

There were some changes made to the planned communication activities in the second part of the project due to the disruption caused by the formal project delay and the Covid-19 pandemic. Despite these issues, significant communication work took place with a focus on digital communication in order to meet the dissemination and communication goals of MegaRoller and ensure a long-term impact of the project.

1 IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The planned communication activities in the second half of the MegaRoller project were impacted by Covid-19 in several ways.

Some project activities were delayed due to the pandemic, which had a knock-on effect on communication activities during 2020 and 2021. Delayed activities resulted in fewer blogs, newsletters and media releases than planned.

In addition, travel restrictions caused the planned feature news story on European TV news station Euronews to be cancelled prior to filming. This was unfortunate as significant effort had been put into arranging what would have been a major communications activity for the project.

The project management team delayed the decision to cancel the planned in-person dissemination workshops until the last minute, in the hope that travel restrictions would be lifted. Unfortunately, the pandemic situation across Europe resulted in the workshops—planned to be the primary dissemination activity—to be permanently cancelled.

In their place, a feature film and series of scientific presentations were filmed and distributed online. While the lack of in-person workshops was unfortunate, the decision to switch to a fully online dissemination process has its benefits. The videos will be available for a much longer period and can be viewed by a far greater potential audience than originally planned. This should result in a much greater impact for the MegaRoller project over the long-term.

2 MEGAROLLER WEBSITE

Throughout the project, the MegaRoller website (www.megaroller.eu) was continuously updated with all recent reports, articles, blog posts, events and other relevant information, providing a single place where stakeholders could stay updated with project progress and results. The following two screenshots indicate the development of the site homepage through the course of the project:

MegaRoller website after launch in 2018

MegaRoller website as of November 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 763959.

As the project progressed, the website changed from a 'brochure' style website describing the project goals into a more of a media site profiling news, blogs, images and video. Videos were given prominence on the website homepage and a dedicated video page.

The project KPI of 2,000 website sessions by the end of the project has been exceeded. As of 25 November 2021, the number of user sessions stands at 3,209.

Following the launch of the final video series, this number is expected to rise significantly in the coming months. In addition, the number of pages per user session (2.77) is significantly higher than average for scientific projects. This shows that the MegaRoller website audience is an engaged one.

3 BLOGS

MegaRoller project partners were encouraged to write blog posts about their work during the project. Science blogs are a proven way of communicating the relevance of scientific results to specific target groups that may not read scientific papers, such as industry management, politicians, and other decision-makers.

RENEWABLE ENERGY

Applying Auditory Neuroscience to Wave Energy Models

This article is written by Patrick May from Lancaster University. Patrick works on MegaRoller together with his former colleagues at the MegaRoller partner...

RENEWABLE ENERGY

Wave Energy: The Standardisation of the Industry

This is a guest article from K2 Management's Pauline Laporte Weywada, a participant in the MegaRoller project. The world's oceans hold vast potential...

#ENERGY / RENEWABLE ENERGY

Wave vs. Wind and Solar Levelised Value of Energy

The potential of wave energy is huge, making it a suitable candidate for being an essential part of the world's electricity supply in...

Example MegaRoller blog posts published on the SINTEF Blog.

The primary channel for MegaRoller blogs was the SINTEF Blog (<https://blog.sintef.com/>) because of the existing global audience of approximately 10,000 monthly readers. All blogs were automatically republished on the MegaRoller website.

A total of 8 blog posts were published during the MegaRoller project, with one still in development at the time of writing this report. As of 7 December 2021, the combined number of page views across all 8 posts was 4,881.

The most popular posts were:

- Wave vs. Wind and Solar: Levelized Value of Energy (3,305 views)
- Applying Auditory Neuroscience to Wave Energy Models (476 views)
- Wave Energy: The Standardisation of the Industry (326 views)

4 PRESS & MEDIA

MegaRoller's initial goal was to gain two mainstream news articles during the project. At the time of writing, five news stories featuring MegaRoller have been published, surpassing expectations. News articles produced throughout the MegaRoller project served dual purpose as press releases, distributed directly to relevant media such as Offshore Energy, which resulted in several media mentions.

News articles published by K2 Management (left) and AW Energy (right).

The Norwegian technology magazine Teknisk Ukeblad featured MegaRoller in a story on the potential for wave energy in Norway, Portugal, and Ireland.

Original story can be found here (behind paywall): <https://www.tu.no/artikler/sintef-forsker-pa-bolgekraft-pa-havbunnen-godt-egnet-for-norge-portugal-og-irland/473074>

Screenshot from Norwegian technology magazine Teknisk Ukeblad.

The news website *Offshore Energy Biz* (previously known as *Marine Energy Biz*) covered the MegaRoller project twice. Their first story was in relation to the completion of the WEC model. They also picked up the 2021 news release on the publication of several new scientific research papers.

MegaRoller Project Reaches New Milestone

Photo: K2 Management

MegaRoller project has reached a milestone by completing an advanced custom structure interaction Wave Energy Converter (WEC) model.

The MegaRoller project is an EU-funded research program over the period 2018-2021. The project will develop and demonstrate a 1 MW power take-off (PTO) for wave energy converters.

The PTO is developed in conjunction with oscillating wave surge converters (OWSCs), a class of wave power technology that uses bottom-hinged plates oscillating in pitch following the surge movement of the water particles in the nearshore zone.

Screenshot from Marine Energy Biz story.

Power Technology also covered the story on the completion of the WEC model.

In 2021, a Bloomberg Quicktake short film on the current state of wave energy (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rneqdWMaAw!>) featured AW Energy's WaveRoller technology and how the MegaRoller research project is contributing to its scale-up.

5 NEWSLETTERS

The external project newsletter gained 53 subscribers over the course of the project, although many of these were internal project participants. It was used as an additional communication channel for press releases and other project-related announcements.

Because of the relatively low number of external subscribers, the newsletter was not prioritised during the second half of the project, with more resources going into the production of content (blogs, video) and direct media relations, which had been proven to achieve better results.

Two newsletters were sent during the project, with a third scheduled for sending in December 2021 to promote the launch of the final video series.

An internal communications newsletter was sent to all partners in 2019 encouraging the sharing of MegaRoller material on the partners' own communication channels. The newsletter included URLs of all blog posts and videos, along with pre-written tweets and other social media posts.

6 SOCIAL MEDIA AND VIDEO

From the beginning of the project, video was chosen as a key communication method with social media being the channel best suited to its distribution. Videos were produced at the beginning and end of the project. The initial videos served to raise awareness about the challenges in wave energy in general and how the MegaRoller project would help. The final videos served to summarise the project results.

Initial project films

In the first half of the project, a series of 9 videos were made in conjunction with the Portugal site visit, a series of interviews with work package leaders, and interviews with several partners. These videos were prominently placed on the project website throughout much of the project and shared on the social media channels of SINTEF Energy and other project partners.

All partners were encouraged to use the videos in conjunction with general promotion of MegaRoller. For example, SINTEF Energy Research used the videos to promote the participation of MegaRoller scientists at the Ocean Energy Europe (OEE) 2019 Conference in Dublin, Ireland.

Facebook post using one of the project videos.

The first project video was published on SINTEF Energy's social media channels, accumulating 3,855 views across all channels. This meant the overall project goal of 2,500 video views was met with the first video.

Final project films

A video series was produced in place of the planned final dissemination activity that could not take place due to the Covid-19 situation. The communications team at SINTEF Energy recorded scientific presentations from each of the work packages and put together a final project film describing the project outcomes.

The final video series is being rolled out over the course of November 2021 to January 2022, and so has not been completed at the time of writing this report. The number of views across the series is expected to at a minimum meet the performance of the initial project films, and most likely exceed it.

THE SCIENCE OF MEGAROLLER

Screenshot of the scientific presentation video series on the MegaRoller website as of 7 December 2021.

While the lack of the planned physical workshop is disappointing, the video series has great potential to meet and exceed the exploitation, dissemination and communication goals of MegaRoller.

The videos will be available for a much longer period and can be viewed by a far greater potential audience than originally planned. This should result in a much greater impact for the MegaRoller project over the long-term.

Video name	Total Views on Primary Platform**
Site visit in Portugal	3,855
Partner Videos	200
Work Package Videos	180
Bloomberg Quicktake	400
Final project film	to be launched
Final project science presentations	just launched

**More views will have been generated on other platforms (for example outlets such as Bloomberg.com and direct social media uploads) for which we do not have access to all the statistics.

Social media

Individual partners were encouraged to use their own social media channels to share MegaRoller progress throughout the project. As outlined above, sharing of videos—in particular the original project film—was a success.

But social media was also used to publicise media mentions of the MegaRoller project. For example, SINTEF Energy shared the 2019 *Teknisk Ukeblad* story on Facebook and Twitter, obtaining more than 4,000 views for the single post.

Social media posts on Facebook and Twitter. 2,400 views on Facebook, 2,000 on Twitter.

As another example, AW-Energy used their WaveRoller-branded social media channels to publicise the project and ongoing work of the MegaRoller partners throughout the project.

MegaRoller was also featured in the social media accounts of media organisations and the EU commission at various points throughout the project.

Two example tweets from the WaveRoller Twitter account of AW-Energy

Two example tweets mentioning the MegaRoller project from Renewables News and the EU Commission.

Other social media platforms used by project partners included LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube. For example, AW-Energy, K2 Management and SINTEF Energy shared their involvement in MegaRoller to an engaged audience of relevant professionals on LinkedIn throughout the project.

Two example LinkedIn posts mentioning MegaRoller from AW-Energy and K2 Management.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 763959.

7 COMMUNICATION KPI'S AND FINAL NUMBERS

The following table describes the planned communication actions and KPI target together with the status in the final month of the project. However, many of the numbers will increase in the months and years to come. This is especially true of the final project video views and website pageviews, as the final video series is expected to generate interest long after the project is finished.

Track	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	KPI	Status Dec 2021
Social media campaigns (through partners channels)	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Social media views in total: 20,000	17,800 views
Project video: YouTube Social Media channels		4 videos	4 videos	Total views: 2500	4,635 on primary platforms (estimated 10,000 total)
Blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	Blog views: 1000	8 blogs 4,875 views
Press releases (inc. media / wire service)	Press release 1 Press release 2	Press release 3	Press release 4	150,000 views across all media	Estimated 150,000 views
Newsletter	1 newsletter	2 newsletters	2 newsletters	100 subscribers	53 subscribers
Webpages	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Pageviews 2,000	3,209